

Analytical Applications of 1-Amidino-2-thiourea. Part IV. Gravimetric Determination of Mercury(II)*

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A new gravimetric method for the determination of mercury(II) has been developed, based on the quantitative precipitation of HgS from ammoniacal solution of mercury salts by 1-amidino-2-thiourea (ATC). Small amounts (16.0 mg.) of mercury can be estimated with an accuracy $\pm 0.2\%$. Addition of a suitable complexing agent suppresses the interference by other cations. None of the anions interferes. Under the experimental conditions employed, 1-amidino-2-thiourea behaves as a selective reagent for determination of mercury.

There is a dearth of selective reagents for the quantitative determination of mercury. In the conventional method¹ of precipitating HgS with hydrogen sulphide or ammonium sulphide, Cu, Cd, Sn, Tl, and Zn and oxidising agents like nitric acid, chlorine, etc. must be absent. Further, HgS precipitate is liable to be contaminated with sulphur. Mercury can be estimated with thionalido², but the results are high if the chloride concentration is not kept low. Numerous elements interfere in the estimation of mercury as $[\text{Cu}(\text{en})_2] \text{HgI}_4$ ² or as $\text{Hg}(\text{IO}_3)_2$ ³. Dithian method⁴ suffers from the disadvantage of interference by Ag(I), Hg(I), Pt(IV), Pd(II), etc. Iron and chloride must be absent in the periodate method⁵. Thioacetamide⁶ has been employed as a reagent for the gravimetric estimation of mercury as HgS. The results are, however, always high and the reagent is not selective. 2-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)benzimidazole is reported⁷ as a selective reagent for mercury. Only Fe(II) and Fe(III) interfere seriously if present appreciably. Recently thiourea⁸ has been used in estimating mercury as HgS, but this method is not free from the interfering effect of Se(IV).

1-Amidino-2-thiourea, $\text{NH}_2-\text{C}(=\text{NH})\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}(=\text{S})-\text{NH}_2$, reacts with mercury(II) to form complexes⁹, which decompose to HgS. This reaction has been utilised to develop a new gravimetric method for determination of mercury.

EXPERIMENTAL

All chemicals were of A.R. quality, except dicyanamide, which was of B.D.H. laboratory reagent grade. The stock solution was prepared by dissolving A.R. mercuric

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chloride in distilled water and its strength determined as HgS^1 . Solutions of the required strength were prepared by diluting the stock solution.

Interference due to several cations and anions was studied by the addition of solutions of appropriate salts. The strength of these solutions was determined by standard procedures¹. Na_2EDTA , KCN , Na_2CO_3 , sodium citrate, and sodium tartrate were employed as masking agents.

1-Amidino-2-thiourea was prepared as described earlier¹⁰. A 2% solution of the reagent was used for the precipitation of mercury.

Determination of Mercury.—On addition of an excess of amidinothiourea solution to a hot ammoniacal solution of mercury salt with stirring, a black precipitate appeared immediately. NaOH was added, if required, to raise the pH of the solution above 10.5. The solution was heated to boiling, filtered through a weighed sintered-bed crucible (G_3 or G_4), the precipitate washed with hot water, dried at $105\text{--}10^\circ$, and weighed as HgS .

Activity Measurements.—A weighed sample was mounted on an aluminium planchet, placed on a thick aluminium sample holder. Activity was measured with a thin end-window (2.5 mg./cm^2 of aluminium) G. M. tube in operation with a stabilised high voltage power supply and a Dekatron scaler supplied by the Atomic Energy Establishment, Trombay. Corrections for background, coincidence loss, self-absorption, and self-scattering were applied.

TABLE I

pH.	Mercury (in mg.).			pH.	Mercury (in mg.).		
	Present.	Found.	% Error.		Present.	Found.	% Error.
0.5	98.80	98.49	-0.30	13.0	60.60	60.52	-0.13
4.0	"	98.63	-0.20	"	101.00	100.90	-0.10
6.0	"	98.88	+0.08	"	121.20	121.10	-0.08
8.2	"	98.81	+0.01	10.5	197.60	197.50	± 0.00
10.5	"	98.97	+0.17	"	296.40	295.70	-0.20
11.5	"	98.63	-0.20	"	107.40	107.40	± 0.00
13.0	"	98.81	+0.01	"	"	107.20	-0.18
13.0	15.96	15.09	+0.20	"	"	107.50	+0.09
				"	"	107.40	± 0.00

DISCUSSION

Table I shows that at all pH ranges, the precipitation of mercury as HgS is quantitative and is instantaneous even at the room temperature. Mercury as low as 16mg. in 100ml of the test solution can be determined with an accuracy of $\pm 0.2\%$. In a few experiments, HgS precipitate was treated with CS_2 to confirm the absence of free sulphur in the precipitate. Mercurous salts also form a precipitate of HgS .

The following anions, added in the form of their sodium or potassium salts, do not interfere in the pH range 10.5-13.0: fluoride, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, sulphite,

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TABLE II

Estimation of mercury in presence of cations.

Cation added.	Reagent added.	pH.	Amount of Hg(II). Present.	%Error. Found.	Cation added.	Reagent added.	pH.	Amount of Hg(II). Present.	%Error. Found.
Ni ²⁺	Na ₂ EDTA	10.5	100.1 mg.	-0.10	Cr ³⁺	Na ₂ EDTA	4.5	108.10 mg.	±0.00
Co ²⁺	"	"	"	+0.20	Cu ²⁺	"	4.0	96.12	-0.08
Zn ²⁺	"	"	"	-0.20	Ag ⁺	KCN	13.0	106.40	+0.30
Mn ²⁺	"	"	"	+0.10	Pd ²⁺	"	10.5	96.12	-0.42
Ce ³⁺	"	"	"	"	Au ³⁺	"	"	95.79	-0.33
Pb ²⁺	"	"	"	-0.20	UO ₂ ²⁺	Na ₂ CO ₃	13.0	96.27	+0.15
Cd ²⁺	"	"	"	±0.00	Al ³⁺	Na-citrate	10.5	96.03	-0.08
Th ⁴⁺	"	"	"	-0.20	Fe ³⁺	"	"	96.27	+0.15
Zr ⁴⁺	"	"	"	-0.10	Ti ³⁺ &Ti ⁴⁺	"	"	96.23	-0.08
Tl ⁺	"	"	106.0	-0.19	Sb ³⁺	Na-tartrate	"	96.20	+0.08
V ⁴⁺	"	"	106.1	-0.10	Sn ²⁺	NaOH	13.0	96.12	±0.00
Bi ³⁺	"	5.5	106.1	+0.10	Pt ⁴⁺	"	10.5	95.04	-0.18

thiosulphate, thiocyanate, nitrate, nitrite, carbonate, phosphate, pyrophosphate, borate, tungstate, molybdate, vanadate, arsenate, acetate, citrate, tartrate, oxalate, cyanide, selenite, tellurate. In presence of cyanide, the solution should be vigorously boiled before HgS is precipitated. If selenite or tellurate is present, the precipitation should be carried out at the room temperature to avoid reduction of selenite and tellurate by amidinothiourea. After quantitative separation of HgS, selenium or tellurium in the filtrate can be estimated by making the solution 3.5*N* with respect to HCl and adding amidinothiourea, when elementary selenium or tellurium is precipitated¹¹. Disodium salt of EDTA does not prevent precipitation of mercury as HgS.

Amidinothiourea furnishes $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}_4\text{S})_2$ with nickel(II) and sulphides with Co(II), Pb(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), Cu(II), Sb(III), Sn(II), and Tl(I). The precipitation of nickel complex and sulphides of other metals is, however, prevented by addition of disodium salt of EDTA. It also prevents the interference of hydroxide-forming cations like Zn(II), Mn(II), Cr(III), Th(IV), Ce(III), Zr(IV), and V(II). Fe(III), Al(III), and Ti(III & IV) form complexes with citric acid when these are not precipitated as hydroxides. Tartaric acid masks the interference of Sb(III). Sodium carbonate is used to form complex with uranyl(II) ions. Sodium hydroxide forms sodium stannite with Sn(II), thus eliminating its interference. Pt(IV) forms a complex with amidinothiourea, which is soluble in dilute alkali. Hence it does not interfere in the estimation of mercury, when carried out at the room temperature. Pd(II) and Au(III) are complexed with potassium cyanide. It also masks Ag(I), which is reduced by amidinothiourea in alkaline or ammoniacal solutions to metallic silver^{10,12}. In presence of Pd, Ag, and Au, the error, however, tends to be more than 0.2%. The results of estimation of mercury in presence of cations are recorded in Table II.

Contamination of HgS precipitate by zinc has been tested by using 245d Zn-65. It was observed that less than 0.07% of zinc was present in 123.7 mg. of HgS, precipitated from solutions containing excess of disodium salt of EDTA and zinc from 0.32 mg. to 1.12 g. and processed through the procedure described under determination of mercury.

In conclusion it may be stated that the accuracy of the present method is quite comparable to those of the standard methods for estimating mercury. Moreover, the contamination of HgS precipitate by zinc is negligible and free sulphur is absent in the precipitate. None of the anions interferes. The interference of all the cations studied can be removed by the use of appropriate complexing agents. Thus 1-amidino-2-thiourea appears to be a selective reagent for the accurate determination of mercury.

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11. Nadkarni and Haldar, unpublished.

12. *Idem*, unpublished.